

GENERAL TRAINING OF HOCKEY PLAYERS

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Physical fitness in hockey is the process of achieving and maintaining such a physical fitness of the player, which determines its high performance in the game. Increasing speed and increasing the rigidity of the game forced to pay attention to the condition players. Athletes who are well prepared physically can and should during the match to remain active both in attack and in defense. Maximum pace throughout the match is the main requirement today's and tomorrow's hockey. The amount of work performed by the players during the match is very high, they "roll" for 5-8 km. The nature of the load follows from the large the number of moving structures when moving with and without the puck. For load indicators should be based on the reaction the player's body to move during the game. To determine the state organism, it is necessary to monitor the change in physiological parameters (primarily ventilation and circulation functions) during the match.

General and special physical training- For the growth of results in hockey, it is necessary to train in two directions:

- expand the volume of general physical training;
- improve the quality of special features of motor abilities.

In accordance with these tasks, physical training in hockey divided into general and special. General physical training is aimed at comprehensive development hockey player, which is the basis for sports specialization. Her goal improve the physical and motor capabilities of the body, circulation and respiratory system, increase the strength of the major muscle groups, as well as expand the stock of general movement skills, in turn contributing to the faster acquisition of special skills, used in the game. General direction of comprehensive physical training, the main features of which are determined by specialization (more precisely specificity) of hockey, the means used must also be appropriate. For hockey, exercises that develop speed, flexibility and agility, dynamic strength and endurance at high speeds. The content of comprehensive physical training in hockey is sufficient extensively. You can use many exercises that do not have on first look relationship to hockey. General physical training occupies the largest

share in the initial stages of the long-term training of young hockey players.

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Age and skill increase share of total physical fitness decreases, and the special increases. However, at some stages annual cycle in hockey players of older age groups are possible various options for the ratio of these types of training, including temporary expansion of the volume of general physical training facilities.

Strength development- Strength is the ability of a person to resist external resistance and overcome it. Depending on the way the muscles work in sports activities A hockey player most often distinguishes between two main forces - static and dynamic. The development of the strength of a hockey player should be approached in two ways: - general (complex) training of both static and dynamic nature, which systematically strengthens individual muscle groups and thus provides the possibility of specific motor structures. In this case, it is mainly about increasing potential strength capabilities of large muscle groups (thigh muscles, back, abdominals, forearms) - the basis for the correct performing a special movement;

Maximum effort method- It is used to train long-term athletes. With such method, the load is submaximal and even maximum (85-100% maximum power) so that the player can repeat exercise 1-5 par The break between the series should last 2-4 minutes. Based on the possible the number of repetitions in a series of exercises is determined by the appropriate weight weights. For juniors and high class athletes exercises at maximum training should be defined in different ways. Conventional means at maximum loads - barbell, gymnastic shells, a machine for training strength and a partner. ranks, a machine for educating strength and a partner. **Method of dynamic loads.** Used to develop the ability to quickly manifest strength. The necessary force load is achieved by the form of movement a certain weight at a faster pace, which provides improved neuromuscular coordination.

Dynamic exercises - require accuracy of all components of the external load. Rest intervals between series -2-4 min. Conventional means: medium and small rods, stuffed balls, barbell, dumbbells.

Reload method- Consists of repeating an exercise with medium (small) weights to mild fatigue. Weight burdens, easy to lift at the first repetitions, gradually approaches the maximum and is physiological impulse to use great force.

This method especially affects endurance during strength development. The method of isometric loads. Used for well-trained hockey players. The duration of

isometric tension is close to the upper limit intensity (maximum 80-90%), should be 4-5 seconds, and when maximum intensity (100%) - 1-2 seconds. Isometric exercise also affects muscle endurance. Duration muscle tension of medium intensity (maximum -60-80%) should be 10-12 seconds, the interval for rest is 2-4 minutes.

Education of speed- Rapidity is the body's ability to respond to a stimulus. (internal or external) by a movement performed in the shortest time.

Methods used:

The method of repeating the movement with maximum effort - the main one in educating the speed of the simplest skills and more complex motor activities. A characteristic feature of this method is long intervals rest necessary for the full recovery of the body before next try. This method is supplemented by the method of dynamic efforts that contribute to the development of strength at high speeds. A method of responding to an unexpected impulse. Nurtures chief way of thinking speed. Used to develop simple and complex (selective) response to visual cues.

Conclusion: The high level of physical fitness achieved in the process of many years of training, allows you to more effectively solve tasks of technical and tactical training and is a necessary prerequisite and basic for achieving high sports results. In general, the physical training of hockey players is aimed primarily to improve health, harmonious development of the body, strengthening the musculoskeletal system, increasing the capabilities of the cardiovascular and respiratory systems, the development of motor qualities. In hockey, as in any sport, the athlete wins. The one who stronger, stronger, faster. And these qualities are needed not only in sports.

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